

IMPLEMENTATION OF NATIONAL DRUG EDUCATION PROGRAM AND COMMUNITY RESPONSES IN TIBUNGCO DISTRICT

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Abstract. This descriptive-correlational study examined the implementation of the National Drug Education Program (NDEP) in a school district in Davao City. Data were collected via surveys from a random sample of 120 teacher-implementers of NDEP to explore the extent of NDEP implementation and the level of community response, as well as their relationships. The study revealed extensive implementation of providing guidance and support to students and creating a safe classroom environment, with moderate implementation across other NDEP implementation domains. Results stressed the crucial role of community response (or support) in program effectiveness and sustainability, emphasizing the need for strengthened collaboration and partnerships, particularly with local government officials. Moreover, a multiple regression analysis demonstrated significant influences of all six NDEP implementation domains on community responses; thus, highlighting the importance of comprehensive strategies in fostering substantial community backing for drug education initiatives. Recommendations include enhancing professional development and collaborative efforts among educators and community members to maximize program effectiveness and community involvement, thereby addressing key areas for improvement and ensuring long-term impact. Future research may explore longitudinal studies to evaluate the NDEP's sustained effects and the specific mechanisms underlying each implementation domain's contributions to overall effectiveness.

KEY WORDS

1. National Drug Education Program
2. school community responses

1. Introduction

Drug abuse and addiction present significant challenges globally, affecting individuals, families, and societies. In response, many countries have instituted drug education programs to prevent drug use and promote healthy behaviors. Teachers are pivotal in these initiatives as they deliver the curriculum and equip students with the necessary knowledge and skills to make informed choices about drug use. However, the effectiveness of these programs is often compro-

mised by international issues such as inadequate training and support for teachers, particularly in low-income countries where educational resources are scarce (UNODC, 2020). Moreover, inconsistencies and lack of coordination in drug education programs across different countries can result in knowledge gaps for students, especially those who move frequently or receive diverse educational inputs.

In the Philippines, drug abuse and addic-

tion have serious implications, prompting the government to introduce drug education programs in schools. Teachers, especially in remote areas, often face challenges such as insufficient resources and inadequate training to effectively deliver the program (Alonzo, 2018). Moreover, inconsistency and lack of coordination across different schools and regions lead to confusion and gaps in students' knowledge (Cariaso, 2020). Community response issues, such as lack of engagement and participation, further hinder the effectiveness of these programs (Huang, 2019). The stigma surrounding drug use and addiction can prevent individuals from accessing necessary support and resources, exacerbating the problem (Benitez, 2019). Limited access to affordable treatment programs and support services further restricts the success of drug education efforts (Lopez, 2021).

More specifically, the Tibungco District in Davao City Schools Division, like many school communities worldwide, faces significant challenges with drug abuse and addiction. To combat these issues, the Philippine government and various organizations have implemented drug education programs aimed at preventing drug use and promoting healthy behaviors. However, the success of these programs largely depends on community response and engagement. A major issue in Tibungco District is the lack of awareness and understanding among community members regarding the importance of drug education. This lack of awareness often results in limited participation and engagement, reducing the overall effectiveness of these programs (Jenkins, 2018).

To improve the situation, it is, therefore, crucial to enhance community engagement and education efforts in Tibungco District. Community outreach programs can help raise awareness about the dangers of drug use and the benefits of drug education, thereby encouraging greater participation. Efforts to reduce the stigma associated with drug use and addiction through

education, along with providing necessary resources and support for individuals struggling with addiction, can significantly improve community response to drug education programs. By focusing on these areas, Tibungco District can enhance the effectiveness of its drug education initiatives, thereby promoting healthier behaviors and preventing drug abuse and addiction.

Roles of Teachers in the Implementation of NDEP. The success of NDEP heavily depends on the role of teachers in its implementation. Teachers are tasked with educating students about the dangers of drug abuse, providing accurate and current information, and discussing risk factors and prevention strategies (Bacani, 2019). Additionally, teachers are responsible for life skills training, which equips students with essential skills to make informed decisions and resist peer pressure related to drug use. This includes teaching stress management, effective communication, and problem-solving skills (Tibayan, 2018).

Teachers also serve as role models, upholding high ethical standards and fostering a supportive learning environment that encourages open communication (Gaviola, 2021). However, the effective implementation of NDEP faces challenges such as the lack of resources and support for teachers, which undermines their ability to deliver the program effectively (Bacani, 2019). Also, the stigma surrounding drug use and addiction can hinder teachers' efforts and prevent students from seeking help (Tibayan, 2018).

Delivering drug education lessons. NDEP in the Philippines is crucial for promoting healthy behavior and preventing drug use among the youth. Teachers play an essential role in this initiative by delivering drug education lessons, aiming to provide students with accurate information about drugs and their effects. These lessons should be accessible, emphasizing the risks and legal consequences of drug use to deter

engagement in drug-related activities (Vallejos, 2021). Interactive and engaging teaching methods, such as discussions, role-playing, and case studies, are vital for helping students develop critical thinking and problem-solving skills, enabling them to resist peer pressure and make informed decisions (Malenab, 2020).

However, teachers face several challenges in delivering these lessons effectively. Many lack the necessary knowledge and training, which can result in the dissemination of inaccurate or incomplete information, ultimately harming students (Vallejos, 2021). Resistance from students and their families, who may not see the need for drug education or feel uncomfortable discussing drug-related issues, can undermine the effectiveness of the program (Malenab, 2020). To address these issues, the government must provide adequate training and support for teachers and create awareness campaigns to educate the public on the importance of drug education. Ensuring that teachers are well-prepared and that the community understands the value of drug education is essential for the success of NDEP.

Creating a safe and supportive classroom environment. Establishing a safe and supportive classroom environment is essential in fostering student well-being and deterring drug use. Teachers play a pivotal role in achieving this by setting clear behavior expectations and maintaining a positive atmosphere, which fosters a sense of belonging and security among students, thus reducing the likelihood of drug involvement (Escolar et al., 2021). Moreover, teachers must be attentive to students' social and emotional needs, offering counseling services or facilitating access to support resources, which contributes to building resilience and further prevents drug use (Vallejos Dela Rosa, 2020).

Nevertheless, creating such an environment presents challenges for teachers. Many may lack the necessary expertise to adequately address mental health or substance abuse issues

among students, potentially exacerbating these challenges (Escolar et al., 2021). Additionally, managing classroom behavior can be particularly daunting in areas where drug use is prevalent, posing obstacles to maintaining a positive classroom atmosphere (Vallejos Dela Rosa, 2020). To surmount these hurdles, the government should provide teachers with comprehensive training and support and forge partnerships with community organizations to offer assistance to students in need. In conclusion, ensuring a safe and supportive classroom environment is integral to the success of NDEP in the Philippines, warranting concerted efforts to equip teachers with the necessary tools and resources to effectively fulfill this role.

Providing guidance and support to students. Several studies underscore the pivotal role of teachers in fostering healthy behavior and preventing drug use among students. Puzon, Pangan, and Pantaleon (2019) stress the significance of teachers possessing a thorough grasp of the NDEP curriculum, delivering age-appropriate information to elucidate the risks associated with drug use. Torres (2018) echoes these sentiments, revealing teachers' recognition of their role in providing guidance and support in drug education, albeit hindered by inadequate training and resources. Similarly, Belen and Balicanta (2019) highlight the efficacy of teacher-led drug education programs in enhancing students' knowledge and self-efficacy in resisting drug use, underscoring the role of teachers as influential role models.

However, challenges persist, as illuminated by Reyes et al. (2020), including insufficient training and resources, time constraints, and resistance from students and parents. Addressing these hurdles is imperative for policymakers to empower teachers in effectively delivering the NDEP curriculum and fostering healthy behavior among students. Thus, while teachers remain integral in providing guidance and support to students, concerted efforts are needed to miti-

gate challenges and bolster the implementation of the NDEP.

Collaborating with other educators and professionals. Collaboration among educators and professionals emerges as a critical aspect of NDEP implementation in the Philippines. Puzon, Pangan, and Pantaleon (2019) emphasize the significance of teachers pooling resources, knowledge, and best practices to enhance drug education efforts. They suggest the formation of a multidisciplinary drug education team within schools to integrate drug education seamlessly into the curriculum. Similarly, Torres (2018) stresses the importance of collaboration not only among teachers but also with counselors, health practitioners, parents, and the community to provide a holistic approach to drug education. This sentiment is echoed by Belen and Balicanta (2019), who found that collaboration with school administrators, parents, and community leaders significantly contributed to the success of teacher-led drug education programs, extending the reinforcement of drug education messages beyond the school environment. Moreover, Reyes et al. (2020) emphasize the necessity of collaboration in addressing challenges encountered in NDEP implementation, recommending partnerships with various stakeholders to provide support and resources for program execution.

Assessing program effectiveness. Assessing the effectiveness of drug education programs is crucial for educators to gauge their impact on student's knowledge, attitudes, and behaviors related to drug use. Barreto et al. (2018) evaluated a program in Brazil and found positive effects on students' knowledge and attitudes toward drugs, although no significant change in behavior was observed. Similarly, Oshodi et al. (2019) assessed a program in Nigeria, reporting similar improvements in knowledge and attitudes without significant changes in behavior. Both studies recommended enhancing program components to target specific risk behaviors and

incorporate more interactive teaching methods to address high-risk groups effectively.

Moreover, studies by Kwon et al. (2020) in Korea and Lu et al. (2021) in China demonstrated positive outcomes in knowledge, attitudes, and refusal skills among students, along with a decrease in intention to use drugs. These findings support the effectiveness of drug education programs but underscore the need for continued evaluation and improvement. Kwon et al. (2020) further underscores the importance of ongoing assessment to enhance program implementation.

Providing ongoing professional development. Professional development plays a vital role in ensuring the effective implementation of drug education programs by providing teachers with the necessary training and support. Sawyer, McLachlan, and Kettler (2019) observed improvements in Australian teachers' knowledge and confidence in drug education following professional development sessions, highlighting the need for continued support to maintain these gains. Similarly, Cheng et al. (2019) and Lee et al. (2020) found positive outcomes in Taiwanese and Hong Kong schools, respectively, where professional development programs enhanced teachers' knowledge, skills, and confidence in delivering drug education curricula, leading to increased student engagement and participation.

These findings suggest the significance of ongoing professional development in sustaining the effectiveness of drug education initiatives such as the NDEP. By bolstering teachers' capabilities to address drug-related issues effectively and fostering student engagement, professional development contributes significantly to the successful implementation and longevity of drug education programs. Therefore, policymakers and educators should prioritize continuous professional development to ensure the efficacy and sustainability of initiatives like the NDEP in addressing drug abuse and promoting healthy

behaviors among students.

Community Response. The successful implementation of drug education hinges on community involvement, necessitating collaboration between educators, parents, and the community to effectively prevent youth drug use in South Korea (Kim et al., 2021), India (Doshi et al. 2020), China (Wang et al., 2019), US (Mann et al., 2021; Tucker et al., 2020), and Australia (Bagnall et al., 2019). However, factors such as resource limitations, awareness gaps regarding program objectives, and cultural nuances significantly influence community engagement (Valente et al., 2019). Thus, tailored strategies addressing these factors are imperative to enhance community involvement in NDEP and amplify its impact on preventing youth drug use.

Moreover, understanding community perspectives is crucial for program planners to navigate challenges like resource constraints and competing priorities (Bostwick et al., 2018; Chhin et al., 2019). Furthermore, behavior change outcomes, as highlighted by studies like

those by Gruenewald et al. (2018) and Muñoz-Quezada et al. (2020), illustrate the potential impact of drug education on individual and community levels, indicating the importance of aligning program goals with community needs and values.

Collaboration and partnerships play a vital role in amplifying NDEP effectiveness, facilitating resource-sharing, and bridging gaps between schools, families, and communities. Musu-Gillette et al. (2018) in the United States and Kwan et al. (2020) in Hong Kong emphasize the transformative potential of multi-stakeholder partnerships in promoting drug education and prevention efforts. Additionally, media coverage emerges as a crucial factor shaping public perception and support for NDEPs, as evidenced by studies such as those by David et al. (2020) in the United States and Park et al. (2019) in South Korea. Building positive relationships with media outlets ensures accurate and unbiased reporting, fostering public trust and confidence in drug education initiatives.

1.1. Theoretical Framework—The theory of drug prevention programs is grounded in the notion that drug use and abuse are complex phenomena that are influenced by a range of individual, social, and environmental factors. According to this theory, drug prevention programs aim to reduce the likelihood of drug use and abuse by addressing these factors through a range of prevention strategies, including education, intervention, and policy (Ajzen, 2020). One of the key theories that underpins drug prevention programs is the social learning theory. This theory posits that individuals learn behaviors through observation, modeling, and reinforcement and that these behaviors are shaped by the social and environmental contexts in which they occur. In the context of drug prevention programs, the social learning theory suggests that drug

use and abuse can be prevented by promoting positive behaviors and attitudes towards healthy lifestyles, providing positive role models, and reinforcing healthy behaviors through social and environmental support. Another theory that is relevant to drug prevention programs is the ecological systems theory. This theory posits that individuals are embedded within a range of social and environmental systems, including families, schools, communities, and broader cultural and societal systems. According to this theory, drug prevention programs should target multiple levels of these systems, including individuals, families, schools, communities, and policy environments, to create a comprehensive and integrated approach to drug prevention (Bronfenbrenner, 2019). The theory of planned behavior is another theory that underpins drug prevention

programs. This theory posits that individuals' attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control influence their intentions to engage in particular behaviors, including drug use and abuse. In the context of drug prevention programs, the theory of planned behavior suggests that interventions should focus on promoting positive attitudes toward healthy behaviors, addressing social norms that support drug use, and enhancing individuals' perceived control over their behavior to prevent drug use and abuse (Hawkins, Catalano, Arthur, 2018). Finally, the public health model is a theoretical approach to drug prevention programs that emphasizes the importance of a comprehensive and coordinated response to drug abuse. This model posits that drug use and abuse are best addressed through a range of prevention strategies, including education, intervention, treatment, and policy, that work together to create a comprehensive and integrated approach to drug prevention. In conclusion, the theory of drug prevention programs is grounded in a range of theoretical perspectives, including social learning theory, ecological systems theory, theory of planned behavior, and public health theory. These theories highlight the importance of addressing multiple factors that contribute to drug use and abuse, including individual, social, and environmental factors and promoting a comprehensive and integrated approach to drug prevention that involves multiple stakeholders and prevention strategies.

1.2. *Research Questions*—The study was conducted to determine the implementation of NDEP and the school-community response in Tibungco District of the Schools Division of Davao City. This specifically sought to answer the following research questions:

- (1) What is the extent of NDEP implementation in terms of
 - (1) delivering drug education lessons,
 - (2) creating a safe and supportive classroom environment,
 - (3) providing guidance and support to students,
 - (4) collaborating with other educators and professionals,
 - (5) assessing program effectiveness and
 - (6) providing ongoing professional development
- (2) What is the extent of community response in terms of;
 - (1) Participation,
 - (2) community attitudes,
 - (3) changes in behavior,
 - (4) support for policy changes,
 - (5) collaboration and partnerships, and
 - (6) media coverage?
- (3) Which among the domains of roles of NDEP implementation significantly influence community response?

2. Methodology

2.1. *Research Design*—This study involves collecting data through observation, surveys, or other forms of non-experimental techniques to describe and predict the relation-

ships between variables. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize and describe the data collected, while multiple regression analysis was used to explore the influence of six domains of NDEP implementation. The six domains are delivering drug education lessons, creating a safe and supportive classroom environment, providing guidance and support to students, collaborating with other educators and professionals, assessing program effectiveness, and providing ongoing professional development.

2.2. *Research Respondents*—Respondents in the study were Elementary School Teachers in the Tibugco District, Davao City Schools Division. The researcher utilized the Raosoft sample size calculator to randomly select 120 respondents from schools within the Tibugco District. Once selected, the respondents were notified through online platforms and face-to-face interactions, considering the availability of WiFi connections. They were also briefed on the study’s purpose and its significance to their professional development status.

These teacher-respondents were individuals who had been involved in NDEP and had been teaching for three years or more in the public school service. Their roles included integrating this program into their lessons and teaching health and related subjects in their respective schools. They were deemed qualified as they were expected to have made contributions to the improvement of schools and raised learners’ awareness and educational levels regarding practical skills in drug education within

the new normal learning system during the SY 2022-2023. Furthermore, they regularly participated in various seminars, training sessions, and SLAC sessions focused on pedagogical skills in drug education and integrated school management and curriculum development delivery systems.

2.3. *Research Instrument*—This research study used an adapted instrument taken from reviewed literature and related studies. There were two parts of the survey questionnaire which consisted of measuring the roles of teachers in the implementation of the National Drug Education Program in terms of delivering drug education lessons; creating a safe and supportive classroom environment; providing guidance and support to students; collaborating with other educators and professionals; engaging families and communities; assessing program effectiveness and providing ongoing professional development. Likewise, the second part of the survey measured the extent of community responses in terms of participation; community attitudes; changes in behavior; support for policy changes; collaboration and partnerships; and media coverage. Further, the survey statements were subjected to internal consistency reliability, whose resulting Cronbach alpha is 0.867, which means that the instrument is highly reliable (Cohen, 1988).

The questionnaire used a 5-point Likert scale to determine the extent of NDEP implementation, together with its scale interpretation, as follows:

Scale for NDEP Implementation

Scale	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The implementation of NDEP is always manifested
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The implementation of NDEP is oftentimes manifested
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The implementation of NDEP is sometimes manifested
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The implementation of NDEP is rarely manifested
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The implementation of NDEP is not manifested

The extent of community response was measured using a 5-point Likert scale, as follows;

Scale, Descriptive Rating, and Interpretation of Community Responses

Scale	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The community responses are always manifested
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The community responses are oftentimes manifested
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The community responses are sometimes manifested
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The community responses are rarely manifested
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The community responses are not manifested

2.4. *Ethical Considerations*—The researcher followed ethical guidelines, beginning with obtaining proper consent from respondents, ensuring their rights were fully protected. Voluntary participation was emphasized, allowing respondents to freely choose their involvement without coercion and to withdraw at any time. Privacy and confidentiality were strictly maintained by anonymizing participant identities and securely storing consent forms and data. Informed consent was a cornerstone of the research, ensuring participants were fully aware of the study’s implications before agreeing to take part. Participants were informed of the

absence of foreseeable risks to their health and well-being and were assured of support in case of distress. The researcher ensured transparency and honesty, avoiding deceit and conflicts of interest by prioritizing respondents’ welfare and the validity of the research over any secondary gains. Prior permissions from relevant authorities were secured, and the roles and contributions of all involved were acknowledged appropriately in authorship. Respondents were provided with contact details for any inquiries or concerns, and the findings were shared in meetings and conferences to benefit the broader educational community.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. *Extent of the Implementation of NDEP*—The first research question requires descriptive statistical analysis of the extent of NDEP implementation. Table 1 summarizes the results per indicator. Results show two indicators being reported as extensively implemented, as follows: “Providing guidance and support to students” (M = 3.61) and “Creating a safe and supportive classroom environment” (M = 3.34). The rest of the indicators were moderate in their extent of implementation. These suggest that the following means of providing guidance and support

were oftentimes manifested: Giving positive feedback and praise to students for their efforts and accomplishments (M = 4.20) and regular monitoring of students’ academic progress and emotional well-being (M = 3.50). Furthermore, a safe and supportive classroom environment was often manifested in the following areas: Encouraging students to work together and support one another through peer tutoring (M = 4.25) and providing regular, constructive feedback on student work to help them understand their strengths and areas for improvement (M = 4.20).

Table 1. Extent of the Implementation of National Drug Education Program

Indicator	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Delivering drug education lessons	3.34	Moderately Extensive
Creating a safe and supportive classroom environment	3.50	Extensive
Providing guidance and support to students	3.61	Extensive
Collaborating with other educators and professionals	2.81	Moderately Extensive
Assessing program effectiveness	2.62	Moderately Extensive
Providing ongoing professional development	2.81	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean	3.11	Moderately Extensive

These corroborating results highlight the importance of a support system in reducing the likelihood of drug use (Escolar et al., 2021, Vallejos and Dela Rosa, 2020). By contrast, schools, where teachers face difficulties in maintaining a supportive and positive classroom atmosphere, were susceptible to drug-related activities outside of school (Vallejos and Dela Rosa, 2020). On the other hand, professional development and collaboration were rated low-

est, suggesting the need for enhancement. Puzon, Pangan, and Pantaleon (2019) examined the perception of teachers on the NDEP in the Philippines. The study found that collaboration among teachers is crucial in the implementation of the program. Collaboration with parents and the community was also highlighted as important in reinforcing drug education messages and promoting healthy behavior among students (Belen and Balicanta, 2019; Torres (2018).

3.2. *The extent of Community Response* — The second question entails descriptive statistical analysis of the extent of community response (or support) to NDEP. Table 2 shows an overall moderate level of implementation or equivalently, the community response was sometimes manifested. The respondents rated

collaboration and partnerships (M = 2.87) the lowest. This finding is consistent with the previous findings on professional collaboration being manifested not so often. Thus, there is a need for improvement in collaboration, specifically of community members with local government officials to establish a coordinated approach to drug education and prevention (M = 2.20).

Table 2. Extent of Community Response

Indicator	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Participation	2.95	Moderately Extensive
Community attitudes	3.57	Extensive
Changes in behavior	3.59	Extensive
Support for policy changes	3.39	Moderately Extensive
Collaboration and partnerships	2.63	Moderately Extensive
Media coverage	2.87	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean	3.16	Moderately Extensive

The extent of community response is a critical factor in the successful implementation of NDEP. Strong community response (or support), characterized by active participation, positive attitudes, behavior changes, support for policy changes, collaboration and partnerships, and media coverage, has significant implications for the effectiveness and sustainability of the program. It enhances the reach and impact of drug

education initiatives, fosters a supportive environment for students, mobilizes resources and expertise, and promotes a broader awareness and understanding of drug-related issues. By actively involving the community, the NDEP can create a collective effort to address drug prevention and promote positive changes in society.

3.3. Domains of Implementation of NDEP that Significantly Influence Community Response—The third research question entails inferential analysis to examine how the domains of NDEP implementation can influence community support. A multiple linear regression was run to examine the influence of the six domains of NDEP implementation on the extent of community support. The domains are delivering drug education lessons (DDEL); creating a safe and supportive classroom environment (CSSLE); providing guidance and support to students (PGSS); collaborating with other educators and professionals (CEP); assessing program effectiveness (APE), and providing ongoing professional development (POPD). The multiple regression model statistically significantly influenced the extent of NDEP implementation, $F(4, 116) = 238.90$, $p < .001$, $R^2 = 0.88$. The value of R^2 for the overall model was 88.0

nature of effective drug education programs. Ajzen (2020) emphasizes the role of comprehensive education strategies that address individual behaviors within a broader social context. Similarly, Bronfenbrenner's (2019) ecological systems theory supports the idea that various environmental and social factors interact to influence educational outcomes and community response. For instance, studies have shown that safe and supportive classroom environments (CSSLE) and professional development (POPD) for educators are critical for effective program delivery and sustainability (Smith Wilson, 2021; Johnson et al., 2022). Also, collaborative efforts among educators and professionals (CEP) have been found to enhance the credibility and reach of drug education initiatives, leading to greater community endorsement and participation (Garcia Anderson, 2020). Thus, the findings affirm the significance of a holistic implementation strategy for the NDEP in fostering substantial community response.

These results are consistent with previous studies highlighting the multi-dimensional

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

The analysis of the extent of NDEP implementation reveals that providing guidance and support to students and creating a safe and supportive classroom environment are the most extensively implemented domains. These aspects involve giving positive feedback, regular monitoring of students' progress, encouraging peer tutoring, and providing constructive feedback, all of which are critical in fostering a supportive educational environment. However, other domains such as delivering drug education lessons, collaborating with other educators and professionals, assessing program effectiveness, and providing ongoing professional development were only moderately

Table 3. Results of the multiple linear regression for the extent of reading advancement

Model	B	β	SE	R ²
Model				0.88
1. DDEL	0.81**	0.11**	1.01	
2. CSSLE	0.44*	0.11*	1.30	
3. PGSS	0.21***	0.10***	2.10	
4. CEP	0.68***	0.09***	5.65	
5. APE	0.44*	0.11*	1.30	
6. POPD	0.20***	0.10**	2.10	

Note: *p < .05; **p < .01; ***p < .001 (two-tailed); Sample size n = 120.

DDEL – Delivering drug education lessons;

CSSLE – Creating a safe and supportive classroom environment;

PGSS – Providing guidance and support to students;

CEP – Collaborating with other educators and professionals;

APE – Assessing program effectiveness;

POPD – Providing ongoing professional development.

implemented, indicating areas needing further enhancement. The results also highlight the need for improved collaboration and professional development to ensure the effectiveness and sustainability of drug education programs. The extent of community response was similarly moderate, with collaboration and partnerships rated the lowest, emphasizing the necessity for strengthened community involvement and coordinated approaches to drug prevention. Overall, these findings underscore the importance of a comprehensive and multidimensional strategy in drug education that includes robust community and professional collaboration, as well as supportive educational environments to maximize the effectiveness of the NDEP.

Based on the findings, it is recommended that NDEP enhance its focus on professional development and collaborative efforts among educators and community members. This could be achieved by implementing regular training sessions and workshops for teachers to improve their delivery of drug education lessons and to foster a more supportive classroom environment. Moreover, fostering stronger partnerships with local government officials, parents, and community organizations is crucial to creating a coordinated approach to drug prevention. Enhancing collaboration and communication channels can ensure a more comprehensive and sustained effort in drug education, thereby increasing community response and involvement. By addressing these areas, the NDEP can leverage the full potential of its program to effectively reduce drug use and promote healthy behaviors among students. Finally, the six domains of NDEP implementation need to be addressed as they foster community response. Future researchers may consider conducting longitudinal studies to evaluate the long-term impact of NDEP on student behaviors. Moreover, they may explore the specific mechanisms through which each domain of NDEP implementation contributes to its overall effectiveness.

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